

LAWFUL CONTROLS OF OWNERSHIP

الضوابط المشروعة للملكية

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أبو الفردوس بينات باشا البجالي

قسم علوم القرآن والتفسير كلية العلوم الإسلامية جامعة المدينة العالمية / ماليزيا

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Abstract

This research deals with some types and forms of ownership that are permitted by the Sharia, including:

Sale: by stating its meaning and legitimacy.

And that is through a statement of its meaning and the draft and the wisdom of the project taking into account the interests of people

Leasing: by stating its definition and legitimacy in the Book, Sunnah, and consensus, and the conditions of the lease contract

The will for money: It was dealt with through its definition, legality and provisions

Reviving the dead land: This is based on a statement of its meaning and legitimacy

Feudalism by stating its meaning, legitimacy and types (feudal ownership, work and exploitation)

ملخص البحث

يتناول هذا البحث بعض أنواع وصور التملك التي أباحها الشرع ومنها:
البيع: وذلك من خلال بيان معناه ومشروعيته بالكتاب والسنة والإجماع، وبيان شروط البيع سواء المتعلقة بالعاقدين أو المتعلقة بالمعقود عليه.
السلم: وذلك من خلال بيان معناه ومشروعيته والحكمة من مشروعيته مراعاة لمصالح الناس
الإجارة: من خلال بيان تعريفها ومشروعيته في الكتاب والسنة والإجماع، وشروط عقد الإجارة
الوصية بالمال: وتم تناولها من خلال تعريفها ومشروعيته وأحكامها
إحياء الأرض الموات: وذلك من خلال بيان معناه ومشروعيته
الإقطاع من خلال بيان معناه ومشروعيته وأنواعه (إقطاع التملك وإقطاع الإرفاق وإقطاع الاستغلال)

INTRODUCTION

Praise be to God, Lord of the Worlds, the Possessor of Majesty, who guides his servants to the lawful provision, and blessings and peace be upon our master Muhammad, his companions and the family, and after:

God Almighty has permitted the Muslim to own money, whether by seeking it through work, or without seeking it through inheritance. Reasons for ownership, and we indicate them; To make it easier for people, by answering these questions:

What do you mean by selling?

- What does ladder mean?

Is leasing permissible?

Is it permissible to bequeath money?

When does a person have the right to own land?

What are the types of feudalism?

We ask Allah to grant us success and acceptance

First: Selling:

a) Meaning of selling:

It is a language: the opposite of something with something, one of the opposites is said: a sale and the other a price, and the sale corresponds to the purchase, except that both words are considered opposites, and the meaning of this is that each of them comes in the meaning of the other; Where the word “buy” can be used in the sense of selling, and “sale” is used in the sense of buying, but if the seller is used in the sense of buying, then the one who comes to mind in the custom is that he is giving the commodity, and the sale according to Islamic law is the exchange of money for money by ownership and possession.

b) its legality

Selling is legal according to the Qur’an, Sunnah and consensus:

the book:

The Almighty said (ثُمَّ تَدْفَعُ فِئْتًا) ()

year:

There are many hadiths from the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, indicating the legitimacy of selling and that it is one of the best earnings, including: The Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, was asked: “Which earning is best? Moreover, he - may God’s prayers and peace be upon him - and his companions, may God be pleased with them, used to deal in buying and selling, which indicates its legitimacy.

consensus:

The scholars, may God have mercy on them, have unanimously agreed on the legality of selling, just as people’s need calls for it and cannot be paid without it, as needs vary, and often relate to what is in the hands of others, and selling is a way to obtain them.

c) Conditions of sale: ()

For the sale to be valid, several conditions are required:

First condition:

Satisfaction from the contracting parties: The Almighty said: (ثُمَّ تَدْفَعُ فِئْتًا) (), and on the authority of Abu Saeed Al-Khudri - may God be pleased with him - that the Prophet - The Messenger of God, may God’s prayers and peace be upon him - said: (The sale is only by mutual consent) () “Consent is known by the explicit saying, or what is indicated by the current actions, the course of the words with the evidence indicating the same, such as writing for the absent as decided by the jurists, may God Almighty have mercy on them, and as for compulsion, the sale is not valid with it. Unless it is right, such as if coercion is underway to achieve an interest or to ward off a corruption, such as when the ruler buys land from a man to build a road on it that people need.

Second condition:

That the two contracting parties may act, as each of them is responsible for rationality. He, peace and blessings of God be upon him, said: “The pen has been lifted from three: from the sleeper until he awakens, from the young until he grows up, and from the insane until he becomes sane.”

The third condition:

That the contract for which the contract is money is permissible benefit without necessity. He, peace and blessings of God be upon him, said: (God and His Messenger forbade the sale of alcohol, dead meat, pork and idols. It was said: O Messenger of God, do you see the fat of dead meat, that ships are painted with it, and skins are painted with it, and people use it as light? He said: No, it is forbidden. Then he said - may God’s prayers and peace be upon him. And peace be upon him - at that: God fought the Jews, for when God forbade their fat for them, they sold it and then sold it and ate its price) () “In this way, the unclean and forbidden objects are removed, and it is not correct for the thing sold to be wine, dead meat, blood, and so on.

- 3- On the authority of Abdullah bin Omar, he said, “The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said, ‘Give the hired worker his wages before his sweat dries up.’”

consensus:

The jurists unanimously agreed on the legality and validity of the lease. ()

c) Conditions of the lease contract: ()

For the validity of the lease contract, several conditions are required:

- 1 - That it is permissible to act and it is free, very rational.
- 2- Knowing the benefit and the fee.
- 3- The leased property should be something that can be used, while its origin remains. Such as cars, homes, etc.
- 4- That the benefit is permissible.

It is clear from the verses and hadiths and the statement of Ibn Qudamah that the lease is legally permissible and there is nothing about it, but several conditions must be observed in it.

Fourth: the bequest for money:

a) its definition:

It is to donate money after death. ()

b) its legitimacy:

The will is legitimate in the Qur’an, Sunnah and consensus:

In the book: The Almighty’s saying: (*وَأَوْفُوا بعهودكم التي كنتم تعهدون*) ()

In the Sunnah: On the authority of Abdullah bin Omar - may God be pleased with them both - that the Messenger of God - may God’s prayers and peace be upon him - said: (What is the right of a Muslim who spends two nights and has something that he wants to make a will except his will written at his head) The story of Saad bin Abi Waqas - may God be pleased with him God on his authority - when he wanted to make a will in his illness that the Prophet - may God’s prayers and peace be upon him - said to him: “One-third and one-third is large or many.”

The consensus: The scholars are unanimously agreed on the permissibility of the will ()

c) Its provisions:

The following provisions shall be made in the will:

- 1- It is forbidden for a person who has an heir if he bequeaths more than one third or bequeaths to an heir something that the heirs did not permit.
- 2- It is sunnah for a third or less for someone who has left a lot of good.
- 3- And you hate the poor and his heir is needy.
- 4- It is permissible for the poor and his inheritors are rich. ()

Fifth: Reviving the dead land:

a) It means:

Al-Mawat: The land separated from the jurisdictions and the infallible property. (), and revive the dead: reviving the dead land that has not been previously cultivated or built (), or a commercial or tourist project is established on it.

b) its legality

Reviving the dead is a project in the Sunnah and there is consensus:

in the year:

On the authority of Jaber - may God be pleased with him - that the Prophet - may God’s prayers and peace be upon him - said: “Whoever revives dead land, it is his.” He retrieved it for not reviving it in a certain period.

In unanimity:

Muslims have unanimously agreed on the legitimacy of revival in general, and the Islamic Sharia has set specific conditions for reviving the land to achieve its purposes of bringing interests to all Muslims and warding off evil and disputing them, and they are shown in their places from the books of jurisprudence (), including: the ruler’s permission, lest people dispute it, and to revive it in specific time; So that people do not become lazy and the opportunity to revive it is lost to others, as Bilal bin Al-Harith did in his story with Omar - may God be pleased with him -.

Sixth: Fettering:

a) It means:

It is that the ruler has made some of the lands inhabited by construction or agriculture belong to some people, so this person is more entitled to it than others under certain conditions.

b) its legality

Feudalism is legitimate if it is for an interest. This is indicated by the Sunnah of the Prophet - may God’s prayers and peace be upon him - where Zubair cut off his “enemy” horse, and he ran the horse until he got up and then threw his

whip, and he said: Cut him as he reached the whip. (). “The difference between mewat and feudalism is that the latter belongs to land inhabited by agriculture or construction, unlike the former.”

c) Its types:

Feudalism is of three types:

- (1) Iqta' of ownership: It is a fiqh that means the imam's ownership of the one who gave it to him.
- (2) Iqt' al-atfaq: which is that the imam or his deputy cut off the sellers from sitting in the wide roads and squares and the like that they benefit from without harming the people.
- (3) Iqti' of exploitation: It is that the imam or his deputy cut off whoever he sees in his fiefdom as an interest in order to benefit from the thing that he cut, and if the interest is lost, the imam has the right to take it back.

Search conclusion

At the end of our research, we can summarize the most important results that we reached as follows:

The legality of selling according to the Book, the Sunnah, and consensus

The interests of the people are carried out in peace

A lease is a contract for a permissible and known benefit

Permissibility of bequeathing money after death

It is permissible for someone who revives dead land to own a plantation or project

- The person has the right to own the land of the dead?

It is permissible for the ruler to allocate some lands to some people if he sees this as an interest

Margins

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() It was included by Abu Dawud, first book of limits, chapter on the insane who strikes a limit, part 4, p.

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- [7]. Ibn Al-Najjar, the ultimate will
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